

Paradigm Shift Comparison: EPEMC vs. The Rest

Comparing PEMC, EU, PU, MU, and SM/BSM

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
Lexington, KY
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Key Words - Crisis - Cosmology - Paradigm Shift

Re: What cosmology has the ability to solve the “Crisis in Cosmology”?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EP EMC¹ ², <http://www.epemcgateway.com>

Dear Readers,

I was delighted to see Ghada’s new video on Thunderbolts Project! And I agree 100%. The change in the cosmology will absolutely result in a strong change in fundamental views, language, and experimental research surrounding cosmological, astronomical, and fundamental physics. Mostly, I think we agree: the funding of high energy physics.

So... what’s my reason for writing a reply? Well, frankly, I don’t think it will be the Electric Universe that is the end point, although I think it is a huge catalyst. In this paper I’m going to make a passionate, but logical sell for EP EMC³: an open-source, cliqueless, cosmology which combines the best facets of the various systems.

How does it do this?

1. By examining the various systems, and finding what makes sense, what’s supported and what isn’t, and making firm decisions about what is included, and what is discluded.
2. By having standards⁴ - perhaps the first in all the altstream - that demand similar rigor regarding the Standard Model, and aiming for a higher energy form of product (paper, video, presentation, experiment, etc.)
3. By being open-source and making the WORLD its peers, and not erudite individuals who can win Nobel prizes and yet write the following (and this is a real quote of a real Nobel Laureate):

“Where planet Earth is two-dimensional, space-time is 4 dimensional” (sic) (see Figure 1)

On 24 Jan 2022, at 12:58 am, Hooft, G. t (Gerard) wrote:

Dear [redacted]

There are so many Crothers papers that I wouldn't know where to start. Can you mail me just one or two of the most readable ones? I understand that the public likes his arguments, oversimplified as they are.

As for "pseudotensors" let me briefly explain what they are and how to work with them. A tensor is a quantity with several components that is defined to follow some transformation rules when, in your description of points in space-time in terms of some coordinate frame, you make a transition from one coordinate frame to another. This is like copying maps of planet earth, when you compare, say, the Mercator projection with various other kinds of grid systems. **Where planet Earth is two-dimensional, space-time is 4 dimensional** and this allows for many different kinds of coordinate frames, particularly when gravitational fields tend to become strong.

Space-time itself can be described by using a tensor called the metric tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}(x,t)$, where x represents position in terms of three coordinates and t is time. This tensor has 10 independent components. Now someone in a space ship flying by, may be using different coordinates so for him/her, the metric tensor looks different. Its components are mixed up, looking different.

Now by differentiating the metric tensor with respect to space and time coordinates, one gets expressions that could describe gravitational fields. You get a **quantity consisting of 24 numbers, and it would have been nice if you could write it as a tensor.** But this is impossible, because if an observer drops by in free fall, this observer senses no gravity field at all. Is a gravitational field always zero then? No, not quite, because you might decide to restrict yourself to observers who are not in free fall but who stay put at some location on earth. That observer will always sense a gravitational field, and he/she may still be able to perform coordinate transformations. And sometimes observers detect gravitational waves. This generates a lot of confusion for people like Crothers: gravitational waves can be measured from a space ship, even if that is in free fall. What is wrong? Well, there may be gradients in the grav. field that cannot all be transformed to **zero at the same time. This is called curvature.** Curvature is a true tensor, **having 20 components in our space and time.** There is no way to transform it to zero, **unless you have (a region of) flat space-time.**

1

https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EP EMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

² https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EP EMC_MIMS

³ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EP EMC

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards?authuser=0>

4. By never demanding something from nothing⁵ nor relying on GNOMES⁶ and the like.
5. By tackling OOPArts⁷ and other difficult subjects in ancillary sciences which touch us directly, and not trying to make vague guesses about things at the supposed beginning of everything⁸, or before⁹, as the case and egoic whim of the armchair scientist [reaching for the Nobel Stars] that day may be.

Let us directly respond to each, and at the end, I will place a short comparison table. As much as I respect the giants I stand on the shoulders of, I will be absolutely frank about each community at this time.¹⁰ I will not bother with flat earthers and the like, as much of that part of the altstream is either misinformation, disinformation, or psyops.

Responding to the Video: is the EU the answer?

Two of the images which were key, in my opinion, were:

Here in Figure 2 we see the proposed paradigm shift that is proposed to be approaching. We would then be in the revolutionary science area, by her reckoning. I would actually say we are past much of that, and now we are getting normal science again, but the language of the SM theorists is lagging behind the defacto shift.

The point being that we really should be focused on:

- Refining our PEMC sciences
- Improving our lexicon
- Educating those that are still stuck in now debunked (even by the mainstream) ideas, like classical black holes, dark matter, string theory, etc.
- Marshaling our patience and using persuasion to win over geologists, cometologists, volcanologists, meteorologists, archaeologists, Egyptologists, anthropologists, paleontologists, doctors, biologists,

economists, etc.

Kuhn Cycle

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/49497635/Converting_GNOME_CDM_Mass_Ratios_joke_paper

⁷ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

⁸ <https://scitechdaily.com/the-big-bang-how-could-something-come-from-nothing/>

⁹ <https://www.space.com/38982-no-big-bang-bouncing-cosmology-theory.html>

¹⁰ Bear in mind my hope for the continual improvement is a sign of respect, not detest.

The third figure is also pretty clear. The Kuhn cycle is describing this as a cyclic issue, and I agree. Model drift is where most of the sciences are, but physics is now in the Model Crisis → Model Revolution stage.

But can Dave Talbot and Wal Thornhill's branded paradigm "The Electric Universe" ©¹¹ do so? This is a bit like asking if feminism can lead to equality between the sexes.¹² It's focused on one pole, and this is, no pun intended, going to polarize the audience. There are people who are Plasma people - like Dr. Peratt¹³ or Dr. Gurnett, Dr. Fridman¹⁴, etc. - and there are people who are magnetics people with significant followings, like LaPointe¹⁵, or deceased Searl¹⁶. And there are also individuals who focus mostly on EMF, such as Wheeler¹⁷, Distinti¹⁸, or Dollard¹⁹, etc. with significant audiences. They have all missed the plasma train almost completely.

So Electric Universe sets out to dominate these three groups with a very unified theory, but has gaping holes in the focus, and a distinct echo chamber:

- SAFIRE has no magnetic generation of significant teslas; all magnetism is purely incidental to the anode
- SAM is an incomplete model²⁰
- Light has not been yet defined as a circuit and treatment of light and gravity has been rather simplistic
- Anatomy of the proposed Aether? Data?
- Mythic focus ignores discussions of planet Uranus²¹ (probably the god Hades²²) and largely Neptune and Mercury
- Hyper-focus on comets, weak focus on asteroids
- Tension with LMH/condensate community²³
- Much maligning of certain theories: gravity waves, black holes, Big Bang, etc., but few proposed alternatives.
- Or weak support of ideas like Dowdye's *Extinction Shift Principle*²⁴
- No attempt to sever tired light from Intrinsic redshift
- Not much dealing with MOND, axions, MACHOs, etc.
- Loss of ability to deal with certain archaeology

¹¹

https://publicrecords.copyright.gov/detailed-record/16324430?query=electric%20universe&records_per_page=10&page_number=0

¹² The data is in: no, it cannot, and is driving not only men, but women into polarized camps. As would be predicted.

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/peratt>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QTMllleD-jQ>

¹⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/d-lapointe?authuser=0>

¹⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/generators/searl>

¹⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/k-wheeler>

¹⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/r-distinti>

¹⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/dollard>

²⁰ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

²¹ Tessa Clark also has noted this issue, however, she unfortunately misidentifies the planet as the god, when the planet was modernly named; however all of her critiques are incisive and worthy of review.

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iODcKNdN5SM>

²³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunberbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

²⁴ This can be inferred from the strange sudden disclusion in Robitaille's LMH theory of electric sun. Yet, this is not able to be reconciled with the surface vortices or solar wind.

<https://arstechnica.com/science/2012/06/why-is-the-suns-corona-so-hot-two-words-solar-tornadoes/>

<https://www.amazon.com/Discourses-Mathematical-Illustrations-Electrodynamics-Transformations/dp/0963447157/>

- Weak focus on Chris Dunn's work on Egypt²⁵, or Birkeland's for that matter
- Probably wrong to assume Atlantis is a motif and archetype alone^{26 27}
- No use of now found Perattian Thunderbolt sites and other top electrogeology from east of the Mississippi (hyper-focus on desert southwest)
- Failure to use ratio math to look at mounds²⁸
- Failure to describe the Origins of Religions²⁹ by tying what was seen to the exact sociological reasons³⁰
- No science-based philosophy extruding from the cosmology that can be used as a mental sandbox for ancient and modern and future ideas, etc.³¹
- No direct explanation for Younger-Dryas event³² or death of the megafauna³³
- No direct attempt to calculate the strength of their favorite subject: Thunderbolts³⁴

It may seem like I am being hard on my EU forebears. I actually admire them quite a lot. However, the EPEMC threshold has rapidly advanced the edge, and there is a growing elephant in the room: EPEMC.

There is also drama between the EU and PU (due mostly to the unprofessional behaviors of B. Davidson³⁵), and this fractures the community. Therefore remaining insular and avoiding the clearly superior EPEMC is problematic after the EPEMC paradigm has already made more progress in finding smoking guns in 4 years than was made in 20 to 50 depending on the subject. It isn't only the use and advantages of web 2.0 and its shoulders. It's the application of electrical engineering rationality³⁶, and Occam's Razor, to a more open approach. It also fails to take advantage of as much older altstream as possible. With the exception of Ev Cochrane, he is very good at this.

For example the EU frequently makes use of doppler redshift, particularly in dating, but they also know the dating is suspect, particularly anything tied to doppler redshift. EPEMC also has this problem, but the difference is that EPEMC does not set out to throw out the baby with the bathwater. We presume where mainstream and altstream meet, and dating *might* be reliable under certain normal conditions, so we can provide a very rough timeline. There are some in the altstream, (J. Conway, J. Cook, etc.) who think you can make **specific dates** on a timeline for these events. They have little to no evidence for this as I can see. And J. West has continued this behavior and failed to make better connections.³⁷ These side threads to the EU community remain problematic in their approach, and open the EU to sharp, and rightful, criticism from the SM/mainstream community.

²⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/c-dunn>

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/36753644/Unboxing_Atlantis_A_top_down_review_of_what_we_know_and_dont_know_about_the_Atlantean_through_Megalithic_Period_continents_and_cities_36_000_2_000_YBP

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IUWEK2eVIBs>

²⁸ These absolutely have to be dealt with, they have the best ratio data around. Smoking gun evidence!

²⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_cou_id_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

³⁰ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

³¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims?authuser=0>

³² https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

³³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4

³⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/s0>

³⁶ IMO the TBP uses Donald Scott far too little!

³⁷ He also is jealous of me, but we'll set that aside, for now.

Rightfully the EU and myself³⁸ have called out the mainstream for trying to steal the works of greater men (and a couple women) without giving credit to them. Also for failing to tell the truth about the Cult of Einstein. However, only the EPEMC has confronted directly, while providing due praise, and opening itself up to scrutiny. The EU community has a serious dearth of scientific papers, although they have many books.

Finally, and this cannot be overstated, because the EU made its bread and butter on mytho-historicism aka Velikovskianism, and yet it has remained stuck in the 80s/90s, while major advancements have been made. For the life of me I cannot figure why there is so little interest in Uranus, Neptune, Triton, Mercury, the Trojan asteroid belt(s), Haumea³⁹, and for that matter NIBIR, EDIN, the awen glyphs⁴⁰, etc. Their failure to understand real Arthurology⁴¹ shows a lack of appreciation for an altstream older than catastrophism's severing from mainstream at the birth of uniformitarianism! The study of Madoc journeys has direct historical bearing upon the PEMC, and this is **completely missed** by the EU adherents. They have seriously wide blind spots. Of course I could say Kentucky is part of the problem, because of Thomas Jefferson (1st American vertebrate anthropologist), and because of electrogeology.⁴² But it's worse than that. It's the entire mound culture and Chinese journey to Cahokia⁴³. There are serious EPEMC evidences in Cahokia and Alleghian culture. I suppose we can be happy the EU doesn't use Edgar Cayce! But why not talk about Michigan Copper's purity? Or about the Amazonian Dark Earths connected to Kithiki⁴⁴? It's not good to ignore useful cross-threaded data. EPEMC covers all the EU, and improves upon it. Without the polarizing drama, or the branding limitations, or echo chamber⁴⁵.

Plasma Cosmology: intimidated by its Younger Brother

Like Enki, Plasma Cosmology is the elder, but weaker brother, to Enlil: Big Bang, which came on the scene and began bullying around the human scientific solar system. It really makes little sense except under an examination of professional bullying and cults of personality. Big Bang's foundations are dubious and it stands upon two faulty legs⁴⁶ and its third is at odds, mathematically with it⁴⁷. Its fourth leg⁴⁸ is mathematically unsound and disproven, as of 1901. Therefore the issue is that this is a shogun: acting as emperor, but not the real deal. Big Bang is not a real cosmology.⁴⁹

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https://www.academia.edu/37558537/The_Predictable_Rise_of_Charged_Dark_Matter_How_Covert_Matter_Hot_Grains_Plasma_in_Dark_Mode_is_pushing_the_failures_of_CDM_and_MOND_into_the_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmological_Paradigm

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https://www.academia.edu/40178988/EPEMC_Opinion_Editorial_Haumea_Ring_Destroyes_Accretion_Model_Why_the_Accretion_Model_AM_is_inadequate_for_ring_formation_as_demonstrated_by_Haumea_favoring_the_electromagnetic_Coalescence_Model

40

https://www.academia.edu/71779697/BREAKING_G%C3%B6bekli_Tepe_Starmap_Skulls_The_Asymmetric_Awen_Plasma_glyph_carved_into_skulls_at_G%C3%B6bekli_Tepe_a_ratio_comparison_with_the_turkey_foot_glyphs_of_Kentucky_Alligator_and_Eagle_Mounds_of_Ohio

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https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

⁴² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

⁴³ <https://www.amazon.com/Chasing-Dragons-History-Piasa-Expanded/dp/194837420X/>

⁴⁴ https://www.academia.edu/39821083/Amazonia_Kentucky_Connection_excerpts_from_AKHA_articles

⁴⁵ In one of my newest papers I include the comments of R. Ashcroft a PEM theorist with serious MU like philosophical bents, as he actively dissents from my paper. That's bold. That's accepting critique!

⁴⁶ Doppler Red Shift and CMBR

⁴⁷ Black Hole Theory

⁴⁸ General Relativity

⁴⁹ https://www.academia.edu/44857386/Opinion_Big_Bang_Not_a_Cosmology

But is Plasma Cosmology? Not really. It is a great scientific paradigm, to be sure. But its failure is to cover anything humans relate to: water and solids⁵⁰. Also, it has little interest beyond the existence of plasmaglyphics and plasmascripts... it is only interested that they exist and can be produced in a lab. True scientific method. But the remainder of the story is how these are the original language all people everywhere spoke, and that it connects mankind to God and gods, as is relayed in the Bible, Vedas, Nahuatl myths, and in the runes of Europe, and even rongorongo. In other words, *PU stinks*... at reaching its best audience.⁵¹

Now it also suffers from this: parasitic invasion. The fact is that solar micronova theory⁵² has no basis, and the real story is better told by the EU, albeit quite a bit less completely than in EPEMC. The fact is we had a different star, whose Diameter Ratio was 1.23,⁵³ and it expanded, ruptured **vertically, away from Earth**, and birthed our gas giants. This DR changed and is recorded in the Cosmic Egg motifs worldwide and is most definitively proven post EPEMC publication of Addendum 2, at the Columbia location.⁵⁴

The EPEMC Megafauna Extinction Series, as well as the Chinese plasmaglyphics series, both validate the EU and PC, and this result is an augmentation in the Electrogeology and Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky series. Why? Because EPEMC is bolder, and has no fear of the SM. There is no worry about tenure, or censure, or censoring, there is only a direct, candid dealing with the facts, with citations from the mainstream, and [quality] altstream, and dealing with people everywhere as potentially equally able to add to the human story. In other words, EPEMC can respect the work of past EU and PU people, by scrutinizing it and placing it all in the giant Vinn diagram that is provided by Extending the PEM Cosmology.

There is, however, a fundamental difference, too. While the PEMC absorbs EU and PU, especially the latter, nearly completely, it maintains that the fundamental issue of the three adherents: EU, PU, MU, is that they hyper-focus upon their portion, and not upon the rest. This means, in my opinion, they will form walls to others *inside* the community, visible to those *outside* the community, giving both ammunition for undue and due criticisms, and scaring away potential "customers" who will stray to dangerous ideas, like micronova theory.

The fact is, as EPEMC has shown, the Suspicious Observers community is not respectful of its host, the Plasma community, and it is scare-mongering the community without rightful data. Yes we know the **entire Solar System Electric Circuit** is changing, but no that does not prove the Earth will flip any moment, etc. For example the reliance upon Vogt is problematic. If he was right, since the Earth hasn't flipped in only 4000-5000 years, then it wouldn't flip again for 7000-8000 years. So where's the fire? Past trends are not indications of future events in precision. And a deep study of the data discludes the ideas of exact repetitive cycles, whatever R. Carlson thinks. Sometimes catastrophes were 900 years apart, sometimes 2000, sometimes 3500 years. In other words, not related to circles, but orbits around a highly dynamic system, which acted semi chaotic due to the chaotic nature of Three Body and Five Body problems!⁵⁵

The fact is that the rock art, mounds, myths, plasmaglyphics and scripts, as well as religious and philosophical motifs all agree with a star death, breakdown, age of planetary and moon gods, and their electrical clashes, and definitely not a solar micronova or a comet event (Zamora et al.). Such an event would **not** be selective in wiping out the megafauna. Ben is wrong. Vogt is wrong. Perhaps even Dr. Peratt is wrong. It wouldn't be the first time a great theorist and scientist was wrong after being so close to being right. But I've not heard him say anything precise on this matter. For sure Zamora is wrong, and Hawass is wrong. But they aren't in our community.

However, and nevertheless, Plasma Cosmology is actually older than Big Bang, and should be respected. But it is not nearly as old as EM theory, which is older than gravity theory by 80 years already. EM

⁵⁰ Sure it covers Covalent Bonds. But almost no one realizes Langmuir discovered these, for which he received a well earned Nobel Prize. Why is this not talked about more? The other phases are reifications of crystal plasmas.

⁵¹ Let us be clear, most plasma cosmologists prefer to hide within the folds of Standard Model's jowls. Only bold, albeit taciturn people like B. Davidson set out to make a "Plasma Universe" argument.

⁵² https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

⁵³ https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

⁵⁴ https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=et7XvBenEo8>

theory could even be said to be Egyptian. But we will not go there. We won't even remind the reader that the Chinese knew about both the Earth flip, and compasses well ahead of everyone else, except the Egyptians.

The Magnetic Universe Obsession Stone

There is no other way to say this. Magnetic only people annoy me. They are obsessed with free energy, rather than True Green Energy⁵⁶, and they ignore plasma and electricity even while using it as evidence. Why don't they just take the magnets off the fridge and pray to them? It's asinine. I wrote an entire massive paper just to deal with this group. Yet, they persist. That their heroes are people like Leedskalnin, who used *electricity* to move stones but couldn't deal with regular life, and obsessed about a ratio (and numerology in general), is not a light point. MU people have a bad PR issue. But they sell "seats." They attract spiritualists like crazy. Why? Because unlike the EU, MU people come along with a plethora of philosophies. Theorists like N. Harramein and D. LePointe takes advantage of these interests in metaphysics to construct false, or conjectural realities, with little regard often to the scientific consensus, or facts. They - MU theorists - ignore data that is inconvenient, and simply say things like "gravity is magnetism." Well, no, it isn't. There is an obsession that you only need magnetism, and the Aether, for which they have ample speculations but no data about its anatomy, to "prove" their theories. In other words they still have two poles. Why the other pole isn't electrical, is not clear at all.

The worst of these is not the Searls of the world. It is the MHD people. They make magnetism "flow" and "discharge" and "reconnect" and "freeze" and it's almost all bologna. The fact is that MHD is a lagging characteristic or measurement by confirmation of electrical flow. It lags by 90 degrees phase, either in parallel (force free) or perpendicular (Lorentz force). But it cannot, and I repeat, does not, describe plasma behavior correctly.⁵⁷ Cannot. Does not. This is why magnetism alone cannot explain solar wind acceleration, or heat, etc. It does, in fact, need electrical charge, flow, and fields. Solar power is electrical: period. And without the dielectric properties, and things like capacitance, you cannot grasp Nature at all. It isn't magnetics that change when you perform acupuncture, it is electric fields.

It really isn't even worth describing all the ways MU is wrong, and I recommend people read the "Magnetic Universe Theory"⁵⁸ paper, directly. If you are one of these, who thinks permanent magnets can generate electricity, please cure yourself by doing experiments and reading my paper. It doesn't mean magnetic pinches aren't magical. Something interesting is happening to the EPEMC proposed PEMbrane⁵⁹, at the quantum level. But it isn't because "everything is magnetism." This is a false god.

By the way, the failure of MU to include or even like QED, QCD, etc. does not reflect the feelings of EU and PU/PC theorists. But all the community gets "egg in its eye" by associating with those that deny the power of quantum mechanical theory, even though we can demonstrate that their explanations are shite.

❖ Do not argue with Nature. Argue with Man. Man is what is wrong... not Nature.

Ray Cosmic 3 days ago

Gravity = Magnetism

REPLY

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https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power

⁵⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vqBmufvMN8k>

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https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

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Standard Model: so “complete” it has its own databank of inconsistent, incompatible extensions...

Dr. Chehade rightly points out the “Beyond Standard Model” issue. But she vastly understates the problem. It isn’t merely that they want to steal EU and PU ideas, or that there are a few outliers, like Bose-Einstein condensates⁶⁰, and Acoustic Shockwave theory⁶¹, etc. It is that there is a mathematical inconsistency, and a repetitious failure to perform routine experimentation, to make grandiose claims or pseudoscientific theories⁶², to gain fame by these crankpot ideas⁶³, to obfuscate the facts about data and saturation⁶⁴, or invention or ignoring of pertinent data⁶⁵, of looking for things a priori⁶⁶, and of hiding behind a cult like position of ideas⁶⁷ and declaring others as incapable of grasping the math requisite to even be allowed to discuss the issue.⁶⁸ And if you fail to bend your mind to “Warped” ideas, it is not the warpers who are warped, it is that you are insufficient to understand the recondite, abstruse, erudite *a priori* ‘facts,’ which had origins in dogma rather than lab (unlike PEMC). They will use words incorrectly, like fabric, tube, flux, jet, rope, dynamo, and gas... while decrying that those who do not agree are part of a conspiracy to hate or destroy science.⁶⁹ ⁷⁰ In other words they pervert and destroy science, and in a socialist like manner, claiming everyone else is doing it (an old Chinese Stratagem⁷¹) These “scientists” or scientism zealots are seriously confused individuals. See the Nobel quote above. The man clearly hates talking about what Crothers is saying about the 1st Order Differential Invariant issue, or the logic involved. And all of his arguments are either *ad hominem* or illogical. But mostly, he is just a fancy-pants Flat Earther.⁷²

Let’s take a brief look at all sorts of these BSM’s with seriously confused issues surrounding them:

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black Hole Theory | - | discluded by observation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cosmic Background Radiation | - | saturation and discluded by Herouni telescope |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Black Body Theory | - | needs modification |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dark Matter | - | mostly baryons, and cosmic dust |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dark Energy | - | just magnetism |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gravity waves | - | not yet measured, falsified data, Poincare’s ideas |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Tachyons | - | never seen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> General Relativity | - | Needs re-doing in PEM dynamics |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Axions | - | discluded |
| <input type="checkbox"/> MACHOs | - | discluded |

⁶⁰

https://www.academia.edu/37913321/Bose_Einstein_Condensate_Cosmology_vs_PEMC_Cold_plasma_Discussing_the_problem_of_replacing_all_forms_of_Dark_Matter_with_an_interstellar_medium_BEC_vs_PEM_UAF

⁶¹

https://www.academia.edu/38017260/Acoustic_Shockwave_Cosmology_Big_Bang_and_PEMC_The_belief_in_emergent_matter_versus_material_rearrangement

⁶² https://www.academia.edu/37972998/Pseudoscience_Cannot_Be_Dark_Matter

⁶³

https://www.academia.edu/38105102/The_Dark_Matter_Scatter_How_the_Dark_Universe_Community_is_fraying_and_in_which_directions_as_a_response_to_the_DM_crisis_How_PEMC_re_unifies_the_camps

⁶⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8IKQMEYYLw&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTDaiwe8Us_YNI4Kjmt8ceRD

⁶⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wjLX0YDuFqY&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTCY9cJqtqSR8OZc001T-bZ>

⁶⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RkObyvzVPYQ>

⁶⁷ https://www.academia.edu/65713466/Schnoll_Effect_the_Relativity_Answer

⁶⁸ As is the claim of men like Prof. Hooft and the Schnoll paper

⁶⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T9q-v4IBGuw>

⁷⁰ Seriously, what a weenie: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vmVdPgkudC8>

⁷¹ Point at the mulberry tree while cursing the locust tree (指桑罵槐, Zhǐ sāng mà huái)

⁷² You can tell this was no mistake because he went out of his way to say that space-time is four dimensional. Admitting there are 3 dimensions is, apparently, just too difficult. How embarrassing!

- MOND - discluded and ignores plasma behaviors
- SUSY/String/M-theory - discluded by LHC experiments, 2015
- Pangea Theory - ignores half the data and expansion
- Static Earth - ignores the facts of the Universe, like growth cycles
- Stellar Fusion - gravity doesn't produce fusion, violates thermodynamics
- Dirty Snowball/Oort Cloud - comets are rock, not ice
- Neutron Stars - pulsars and magnetars better explained as pinches
 - Neutrons in general can be simplified to positron-electron pairing
- Accretion Theory - never worked in simulation or observation, Haumea etc.
- Almost all Egyptology - See: Chris Dunn
- Almost all Arthurology - See: Wilson & Blackett and Dr. MacCann
- In a way: modern biomedicine - See: CDNs and electrodynamics, DNA antennas, etc.

What happened in each of these theories? In each one, the underlying theme is an ignoring (despite its use and power on modern living, and because of or despite the fact of a conspiracy by government and big power business money to deny and not teach) **electrical theory**. That's almost entirely it. Some of the later examples are also matters of flat ignoring archeological, mytho-historical, socio-political, and matters of chemistry and physics, data and evidence at specific, key sites. On occasion burying, obfuscating or *even burning and destroying* evidence (by the Smithsonian and others). Then there are the crankpot theories which have half truths or no truths, which are promulgated by a lone crank (like Oort) for so long, or find footing in fanciful science fiction which influences impressionable young minds, eg. black holes/wormholes/warp drives, etc. These ideas become veritable facts *in the minds of these young, eager scientists*, and it's not like they have the ethics to not falsify data, they lack the ethics to admit when they are wrong, and to publish the truth. Some fire researchers. Some throw away their experiments. Some just lie. The worst trash of the lot, like Shapley, Sagan, and Shermer vilify and attack the persons of their rivalry (like Hubble and later Velikovsky and Hancock). These trashy individuals need to be called out and censured, even posthumously. Their behaviors are seriously psychotic and sociopathic, and dangerous in the extreme. Some were even defacto Nazis, while men like Oppenheimer were no longer Nazis but crushed anyway. In other words: humans humaning. Or as the kids say, 'hoomans'⁷³.

Some of the theories are superfluous, too, given there are other ways to understand mechanics, dynamics, heat, etc. Some are just suffering because they lack a good explanation for gravity or light⁷⁴, or a strong foundation for an atomic model⁷⁵ which explains all of the facts, and not just some of it but only with grave guesstimations and mind altering mental-gymnastics.

In every case, though, PEMC can succinctly cure the malady, and find supporting evidence from mainstream and altstream research. It can, in short, correct the nonsense.

All the extensions of EPEMC are literally extensions beyond the cosmology, therefore, and not addons or patches in a sinking ship. Black Holes, for example, are mathematically diametrically opposed to the Big Bang. But in PEMC the Big Bang is a farce, and black holes are merely Bostick's plasmoids on a massive scale. Given classical black holes do not exist, then we can easily, easily deal with M87 as a BSP, and not worry about falsifying the entire theory. That is not the case for SM. M87 is a direct threat, and not a boon, to their ideas. The irony is that the images produced are, in fact, pseudo scientifically derived. But that is a matter for another time. Needless to say, it is not a threat to PEMC. It is either a boon, or non-sequitur.

⁷³ Indicating alien related behaviors. In other words, not grounded in reality.

⁷⁴ https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

⁷⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models>

Table 1 - Random Selection of Comparisons

<i>Deals Logically With:</i>	EU+PC	LMH & Condensates	MU	SM/BSM	MOND	EPEMC
Big Bang	Refutes	Disproves		Disclodes ⁷⁶	Modifies	Disclodes
Black Holes	Denies	Disproves	Attempts	Modifies	Modifies	Identifies
Electric Fusion		Denies	Fusors?	Ignores		TWE
Ultracold		Alternate		Bose		
Electrogravity				Denies		UAF=PEMF
Double Layers						
Electric Nebula						
Pulsars						
Magnetars						
Dinosaurs						
Ancient Stone			Coral Castle			
OOPArts	Petrification		Aliens			
Electrocomets						
Meteorology						PEMS
Weird Water						HEGEME
Cliquishness	Criticizes ⁷⁷	Criticizes	Criticizes	Cult of Einstein	Criticizes	Open-source
Conspiracies	Documents		Obsesses			MMO ⁷⁸
War						Strategy Ser.
History			Aliens	Chronology		
Religion/Myth						
Philosophy			Numerology			MIMS
Medicine				Poisons		CDN theory
Language						Plasmascript
Internal Critique				Erroneous ⁷⁹		

⁷⁶ Literally self-debunking... see Methusela Star

⁷⁷ Yet is itself, quite cliquish

⁷⁸ Means, Motive, and Opportunity as a standard. Evidence required.

⁷⁹ Literally: lacks self-awareness to see the internal critiques from a "Bigger Picture"

Note on previous page: boxes imply *should* be capable of dealing with. White blanks means conspicuously absent. Dark Green means tries too hard or focuses too hard, and light is opposite. Yellow is ignores. Red means the paradigm is far off of reality. Orange means that there is a misguided attempt or even failure to attempt to deal squarely with the issue. The darker the red, the worse the problem (usually more entrenched).

Various systems like SUSY are so disconnected from reality, they aren't even worth including in the table. So as you can see, while a EU (modified with some PU boons it always tends to agree with) does a fairly excellent job improving upon the SM and outstripping it, there are some glaring holes. Those get worse with the discussion of the items on pages 6 and 7. If it did a good job, I wouldn't have invented PEM theory in the first place. The fact that I have not *yet* tackled dinosaurs is more a reflection on lack of time, and openness to speculations, than a glaring hole. It just isn't important at this juncture, except to note they are too large for present gravitic conditions, therefore HEGEME theory⁸⁰ gets ahead.⁸¹

I am not against EU theory, Wal (a friend of sorts), or the Thunderbolts Project in general. However, one advantage of not being inside their echo chamber is I can see what others see, while also trying to deal with a better data/evidence set. And I agree the language will evolve and be modified. Indeed I said the SM would steal the EU/PU "thunder" (pun intended), and not give credit. Eg.: stellar electric fields⁸². However, I disagree with the manner in which the EU deals with it from the side, insularly. Criticizing without getting directly involved is to allow astro "physicists" to continue to beat up or beat down their betters: HEP/Plasma physicists and deny the very real, factual phenomena in present experimental physics, and in mytho-historical studies. My critique of these bullies is almost as vociferous as that of SM archeology, but that's a topic for another paper⁸³, or three.

Sincerely,
Sf. Ramon Careaga

⁸⁰

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

⁸¹ A second PEMS and a new HEGEME paper, as well as another Ashes of Atlantis will be coming out this spring.

⁸² Do you think these scientists plan to acknowledge R. Juergens and H. Alfvén? Not a chance.

⁸³ Nevertheless, I've made a good start in Intro and Part 1 of Megafauna Extinction Series.

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